

CRITICAL THINKING IN PRIMARY EDUCATION

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Abstract: This thesis presents the opinions and comments on the formation of critical thinking skills of primary school students, as well as the fact that teachers should be integrated in the curriculum with more practical activities. Critical thinking of students and changing their attitudes towards their work is very important in forming the ability of independent creative thinking in students.

Key words: Critical thinking, teachers' opinions, teacher training, primary education, European schools.

Critical thinking recognizes the importance of strengthening the education system to build students' thinking skills. Children's critical thinking skills mean, on the one hand, reasoning using fact-based knowledge and embracing open and inquiring thinking. At this point, the following words of President Sh.M. Mirziyoyev come to mind: "Critical analysis, strict discipline and personal responsibility should be the daily rules of every leader's activity." If we teach critical analysis to our growing students from a young age, as the head of our state said, we believe that these students will become mature cadres of our country in the future. However, in order to achieve this, schools need to integrate more practical activities into the curriculum to improve critical thinking. Although teachers, psychologists, and philosophers agree on the importance of critical thinking, there is still no agreement on what the concept means, and there is still debate about how teachers should be prepared to use it in practice. The main purpose of this study was to explore how primary school teachers perceive this concept and how they bring critical thinking experience to their schools as a professional background. A total of twenty-one teachers in three European schools in Brussels, Belgium were interviewed through semi-structured interviews. The results of this study indicate that teachers have a good understanding of the concept of critical thinking. They consider critical thinking to be the ability to analyze facts through various strategies, to perceive other hypothetical situations, and to form and refine personal opinions about concrete facts. According to the teachers, these are the main characteristics of a critical thinker: thinking about different cultural issues, collaboration, analytical and open thinking. In school teacher education, the results show, on the one

hand, that mind mapping, group discussion and critical thinking are relevant practices to consider for active learning and development in the classroom. On the other hand, they emphasize that their experience is still limited. Regarding their professional experience, they indicate that they have encountered project-based learning and the promotion of critical thinking through philosophy for children during teacher training. At the same time, they emphasize that there is still a need for additional support in this area through peer learning and the sharing of best practices in teacher training.

Critical thinking and learning can only happen when educators understand and appreciate the diversity of ideas and experiences. Critical thinking "does not occur in a single-right-answer mentality process. Developing critical thinking is not an easy task. It is not a task that is completed and forgotten at a certain age. At the same time, there is no perfect path to critical thinking. But there is a set of specific learning conditions that help to form critical thinkers. For this:

- to give time and opportunity to acquire the experience of critical thinking;
- giving students and young people an opportunity to think;
- acceptance of different ideas and thoughts;
- ensuring the activity of students in the educational process;
- it is necessary to convince students not to laugh;
- to instill a sense of confidence in the ability of every student-youth to think critically;
- it is necessary to appreciate the occurrence of critical thinking.

In this regard, students:

- gaining self-confidence and understanding the value of one's own thoughts and ideas;
- active participation in the educational process;
- listen carefully to different opinions;
- he should be ready to form his judgments and to return from them.

In conclusion, it is worth noting that teachers should be better prepared to teach critical thinking through existing practices in order to be adequately prepared to promote it in primary education. Focusing on teachers' perceptions, this study helps identify the rationale for promoting "practical contexts for critical thinking" in the context of the professional development of elementary school teachers. The relevance of the results can be used for future educational research and design among different stakeholders (teachers, school principals, policy makers, researchers) involved in innovative teaching methods in "Practical Contexts of Critical Thinking".

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